

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF 1 : 1 COMPLEXES OF Pr(III) WITH HYDRAZINE, HYDROXYLAMINE AND PHENYLHYDRAZINE ($\mu=1.0 M KCl$)

	log K		ΔH kcal/mole for difference of 10°	ΔG kcal/mole		ΔS cal/degree/mole	
	25°	35°		25°	35°	25°	35°
Hydrazine	3.4	3.0	-17.8	-4.7	-4.2	-43.9	-44.3
Hydroxylamine	3.1	2.9	-10.5	-4.2	-4.1	-21.1	-21.1
Phenylhydrazine	3.0	2.6	-13.1	-4.1	-3.7	-30.3	-30.3

prepared in double distilled water. The metal solution was prepared by dissolving the metal oxide in minimum hydrochloric acid and was standardized with EDTA³.

In the test electrolytic solutions, the concentration of Pr(III), potassium chloride and gelation was 2.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.01%, respectively. Ligand concentration was varied from 1.0 to 10.0 mM in each case. Ionic strength was maintained with potassium chloride at 1.0 M. Sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid were used to adjust the pH of the test electrolytic solutions at 2.40 ± 0.02 .

Polarograms were recorded on an automatic pen recording polarograph (C.I.C., Baroda). The capillary used had a m' value of 2.15 mg/sec and drop time of 3.10 sec/drop at 44.0 cm effective height of mercury. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the solution for deoxygenation. Elico digital pH meter (Model LI-120) was used to measure the pH of the test electrolytic solutions.

Results and Discussion

Pr(III) gives a well defined reversible three electron reduction wave at pH 2.40²⁻⁵ in 1.0 M potassium chloride with 0.01% gelation used as a maximum suppressor. The log plot slopes come to the order of 20 ± 1 mV for Pr(III) and its complexes with all the three ligands indicating reversibility of the electrode process. The waves for metal ion and its complexes were found to be diffusion controlled as revealed from the straight line plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} , the reduction of Pr(III) at pH 2.40 \pm 0.02 was -1.81 V vs SCE. The half-wave potential shifted to more negative values on increasing the concentration of ligand. Lingane's⁶ method has been used to determine the composition and stability of complexes (Table 1). Thermodynamic parameters (Table 1) were calculated from the well known thermodynamic relations⁷. The order of stability constants of the complexes is $[Pr(C_6H_5NHNH_2)]^{3+} < [Pr(NH_2OH)]^{3+} < [Pr(NH_2NH_2)]^{3+}$.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (F.K.) is thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. F. KHAN and A. V. MAHAJANI, *J. Inst. Chem. (India)*, 1983, in press.
2. F. KHAN and A. V. MAHAJANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 297.
3. F. J. WELCHER, "The Analytical Uses of Ethylenediamine Tetraacetic Acid", D. Van Nostrand Company, Inc., 1957, p. 174, 181.
4. G. R. ESTRE and G. GLOCKER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 1844.
5. K. S. PITRE and V. K. CHITALE, *Convention of Chem.*, 1979, Anal. 5.
6. J. J. LINGANE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, 29, 1.
7. K. V. YATSMIRSKII and V. P. VASILIEV, "Instability of Complex Compounds", Pergamon Press, London, 1960, p. 60.

Thermal Stability of *m*-Xylene-formaldehyde Resin and Its Derivative

RAJNI PATEL, KANTI PATEL* and RAMAN PATEL

Department of Chemistry, Sardar Patel University,
Vallabh Vidyanagar-388 120

Manuscript received 23 June 1983, accepted 27 October 1983

LITERATURE¹⁻³ reveals that products resulting from nitration and chlorination of a resin had better thermal stability than the parent resin. There was dramatic increase in char yield and a decrease in maximum rate of weight loss for nitro-substituted system compared to their non-nitrated analogues². It was therefore believed that the substitution on a polymer backbone played an important role in the thermal stability. In the present work, the derivatives of *m*-xylene-formaldehyde resins were prepared and their thermal behaviour studied.

Experimental

The chemicals used were of analytical grade. *m*-Xylene-formaldehyde (*m*-XF) resin was prepared using *m*-xylene and paraformaldehyde with *p*-toluenesulphonic acid as catalyst⁴. The experimental conditions for nitration and chlorination of *m*-XF resin were the same as those of *p*-XF resin³. The experimental details for characterization of the samples are the same as reported earlier³.

Results and Discussion

The results are given in Tables 1 to 2. The yield of nitrated *m*-XF resin was 1.2 g. It was yellow amorphous in nature, insoluble in organic solvents and melted above 200°. Parent *m*-XF resin had a melting point of 100° and an \bar{M}_n of 742. The yield of chlorinated *m*-XF resin was 3.5 g and it was soluble in toluene, benzene and carbon tetrachloride. It was yellow amorphous in nature having a melting point of 95° and an \bar{M}_n of 1000.

TABLE 1a—KINETIC PARAMETERS (TG) OF *m*-XF RESIN

R.H. (°C.min ⁻¹)	Amount mg	Decomposi- tion temp. °C	Weight loss %	Chatterjee E_A (kJ.mol ⁻¹)	Order of reaction n
6.5	50	300-650	100	60	1.0
	25	300-650	100	59	1.0
4.0	50	320-645	100	70	1.1
	25	320-645	100	71	1.1
2.5	50	350-640	100	85	1.4
	25	350-640	100	89	1.4
1.0	50	360-635	100	106	1.4
	25	360-635	100	104	1.4

TABLE 1b—KINETIC PARAMETERS (TG) OF NITRATED *m*-XF RESIN

R.H. (°C.min ⁻¹)	Amount mg	Decomposi- tion temp. °C	Weight loss %	Chatterjee E_A (kJ.mol ⁻¹)	Order of reaction n
6.5	50	230-410	27	33	1.0
		410-620	73	34	1.0
	25	230-410	30	33	1.0
4.0	50	410-620	70	92	1.0
		240-400	25	44	1.1
	25	400-620	75	96	1.1
	240-400	25	42	1.1	
2.5	50	400-610	75	97	1.1
		250-410	25	52	1.0
	25	410-600	75	106	1.3
	250-410	25	51	1.0	
1.0	50	410-610	75	105	1.3
		265-415	20	53	1.3
	25	415-610	80	107	1.0
	265-415	20	52	1.3	
		415-600	80	109	1.0

TABLE 1c—KINETIC PARAMETERS (TG) OF CHLORINATED *m*-XF RESIN

R.H. (°C.min ⁻¹)	Amount mg	Decomposi- tion temp. °C	Weight loss %	Chatterjee E_A (kJ.mol ⁻¹)	Order of reaction n
6.5	50	210-425	30	82	1.0
		425-660	70	89	1.0
	25	210-425	30	77	1.0
4.0	50	425-660	70	93	1.0
		225-420	25	92	0.8
	25	420-645	75	92	1.0
	225-420	25	87	0.8	
2.5	50	420-645	75	97	1.0
		235-410	25	86	0.9
	25	410-630	75	102	1.0
1.0	50	235-410	25	88	0.9
		410-630	75	104	1.0
	25	240-415	25	94	1.1
	415-620	75	112	1.1	
		240-415	25	95	1.1
		415-620	75	114	1.1

TABLE 2—KINETIC PARAMETERS (DTA)

Resin	R.H. (°C.min ⁻¹)	Peak temp. °C	Reich method E_A (kJ.mol ⁻¹)	Order of reaction n
<i>m</i> -XF resin	6.5	515	275	1.4
	4.0	505	251	1.4
	2.5	500	265	1.5
	1.0	495	279	1.5
Nitrated <i>m</i> -XF resin	6.5	380 (h*)		
		510	135	0.8
	4.0	375 (h)		
		500	168	0.8
	2.5	370 (h)		
Chlorinated <i>m</i> -XF resin	1.0	480	176	1.0
		350 (h)		
		460	220	0.8
	6.5	480	230	1.2
	4.0	475	248	1.2
	2.5	460	252	0.9
	1.0	455	260	1.0

h*—hump.

The ir spectra of nitrated *m*-XF resin showed a strong absorption peak at 1542 cm⁻¹ assigned to the asymmetric stretching of —NO₂ group and a peak at 1345 cm⁻¹ due to symmetric stretching of —NO₂ group. This clearly indicated the presence of nitro group on aromatic nuclei. Chlorinated *m*-XF resin showed a strong absorption band around 725 cm⁻¹ suggesting the presence of —CH₂Cl groups.

The nmr spectra of chlorinated *m*-XF resin showed a chemical shift at 4.8 ppm for methylene group attached to chlorine and aromatic ring. It confirmed the chlorination of methyl groups.

The above results showed that the number of repeat units in a chain of *m*-XF resin was about 6 and hence the number of chlorine atom per molecule of chlorinated *m*-XF resin was about 7. Nitrogen from the elemental analysis data of the nitrated *m*-XF resin was 1.5%.

The kinetic parameters of *m*-XF resin and its derivatives obtained from thermogravimetry (TG) at different rates of heating (R.H.) in air and using the Chatterjee⁵ method are given in Tables 1a to 1c. For *m*-XF resin, the decomposition temperature ranges were different for different heating rates (Table 1a). A single step degradation was observed with 100% weight loss at all the four heating rates. The decomposition of *m*-XF resin started from ~300° and ended at ~650°. The activation energy (E_A) obtained from TG study using Chatterjee method ranged from ~59 to ~106 kJ.mol⁻¹ and the decomposition followed nearly a first order kinetics. In nitrated *m*-XF resin and chlorinated *m*-XF resin, two distinct steps were observed in the mode of decomposition (Tables 1b and 1c). The major decomposition (~75%) for both the derivatives took place in the second step. The decomposition range and starting temperature for all the resins were different. This clearly indicated that the mode of decomposition was different for all the three resin samples, thereby suggesting that substitution of nitro- and chlorine group played an important role in thermal stability. The E_A calculated using

Chatterjee method at different R.H. varied from ~33 to ~109 kJ. mol⁻¹ for nitrated *m*-XF resin and from ~82 to ~114 kJ. mol⁻¹ for chlorinated *m*-XF (Tables 1b and 1c). The stability as revealed from the TG has the order *m*-XF > nitrated *m*-XF > chlorinated *m*-XF.

The kinetic data calculated according to Reich⁶ method from differential thermal analysis (DTA) showed that the order of degradation for all the resin samples was different at different R.H. (Table 2). The DTA thermogram for all the three resin samples at different R.H. were exothermic in nature. The DTA curves for nitrated *m*-XF resin showed a hump before the exothermic peak.

Summarising the kinetic parameters obtained from DTA and TG it is found that the E_A increased as the R.H. decreased. This might be ascribed to the relaxation time, τ , and regrouping of the molecules as explained before³. In absence of the detailed analysis of the volatile product and the residues to be collected at various temperatures, it is difficult to explain the detailed mode of decomposition of the resin sample studied.

References

1. H. C. ANDERSON, *SPE Trans.*, 1962, 2, 202; *Chem. Abs.*, 1962, 57, 11365h.
2. G. J. FLEMING, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1969, 13, 2579.
3. R. PATEL, K. C. PATEL, B. N. MANKAD and R. D. PATEL, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1980, 89, 561.
4. R. PATEL, K. C. PATEL, B. N. MANKAD and R. D. PATEL, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1979, 88A, 371.
5. P. K. CHATTERJEE, *J. Polym. Sci.*, 1965, A3, 4253.
6. L. REICH, *Die Makromol. Chemie*, 1969, 123, 43.

Studies on Some Thiosemicarbazones and 1,3,4-Thiadiazolines as Potential Antitubercular and Antibacterial Agents

H. K. SHUKLA, N. C. DESAI, R. R. ASTIK
and

K. A. THAKER

University Department of Chemistry, Bhavnagar University,
Bhavnagar-364 002

Manuscript received 24 January 1983, accepted 19 July 1983

THE discovery of tibione [*p*-acetamino benzaldehyde thiosemicarbazone]¹ as a reputed clinically active tuberculostat brought to fore-front thiosemicarbazones² as a group of antitubercular agents.

Thiosemicarbazide has been prepared by following the method of Kozokov and Vostovskii³. The initial amine was treated successively with carbon disulfide, sodium chloroacetate and hydrazine hydrate to get the thiosemicarbazide on cooling. This thiosemicarbazide was then condensed with

different aromatic aldehydes to furnish thiosemicarbazones which have been cyclised by alkaline $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$ in alcohol.

Experimental

2,6-Xylidene (0.1 mole) was dissolved in ethanol (95% ; 50 ml) and NH_4OH (20 ml) was added to it. The reaction mixture cooled below 30° and carbon disulfide (8 ml) added slowly during 15 min with shaking. After complete addition of CS_2 the solution was allowed to stand for 1 hr. Sodium chloroacetate (0.1 mole) was added to it. During this addition the reaction mixture usually got warm and changed colour from red to yellowish green. To it 50% of hydrazine hydrate (20 ml) was added. The mixture was warmed gently, filtered and boiled to half of its volume and kept overnight. Next day, the product thiosemicarbazide is filtered, recrystallised from ethanol (95%) ; m.p. 205° (m.p. reported 204°)⁴.

(a) *Thiosemicarbazones* : To a boiling solution of an aromatic aldehyde (0.01 mole) in ethanol (95% ; 50 ml), the thiosemicarbazide (0.01 mole) in ethanol was added and the mixture refluxed for 2 hr on a water bath. It was cooled and recrystallised from ethanol (95%).

(b) *1,3,4-Thiadiazolines* : Thiosemicarbazone in ethanol (95% ; 50 ml) and NaOH with a little water (solution) was warmed on a water bath and a solution of potassium ferricyanide (5%) was added dropwise until precipitation took place. The contents were warmed for 5 min, cooled and filtered. The product so obtained was washed with hot water to remove excess $K_3[Fe(CN)_6]$, crystallised from ethanol or methanol. The data of these compounds (a) and (b) are recorded in Tables 1 and 2.

Pharmacological screening :

These thiosemicarbazones and 1,3,4-thiadiazolines were screened for antitubercular and antibacterial activity.

Tuberculostatic activity :

In vitro antitubercular activity of the synthesised compounds were studied against $H_{37}R_v$ strain of